

V. 1 Jan 2026

Brand Manual & Visual Identity Guidelines

PlaceMUS XR | Digital Journey across Musical Places in Europe and Extended Realities

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V. 1 Jan 2026

Concept & Logo

PlaceMUS XR develops digital tools to explore Europe's **musical places** and **objects** through **immersive virtual** and **augmented reality experiences**.

The project connects **sound, space and memory** in a **multisensory digital journey**, combining **tangible and intangible heritage** and supporting curators in designing sound-based cultural experiences.

Location Pin

Place · Location ·
Cultural sites

Sound Waves

Sound · Diffusion ·
Echo

Golden Ratio

Harmony · Nature ·
Architecture

Music

Places

Digital Tools

Intangible Heritage

Connection

Memory

Experiences

Belonging

The symbol was designed to translate sound and space into a **layered visual form**, where **acoustic resonance** and **spatial depth** merge into a single, continuous structure.

The PlaceMUS XR logo is shown above in its standalone form to illustrate the project's visual identity; however, in all official communication and dissemination materials it **must be presented in its co-branded version with the ECHOES** symbol, shown below, in accordance with the ECHOES co-branding guidelines.

PlaceMUS^{XR}

When applying the PlaceMUS XR logo, **sufficient clear space** must always be preserved around it to ensure legibility and to maintain visual balance and compositional clarity with surrounding elements.

The full-colour version is the primary PlaceMUS XR logo and should be used whenever possible; monochromatic versions are provided as well **to ensure adequate contrast and legibility when applied to different backgrounds**, as shown in this slide.

The PlaceMUS XR logo **must not be modified in shape, colour or composition**; elements from different versions must not be mixed, and the appropriate version should always be selected to **ensure sufficient contrast and legibility** against the background.

Without ECHOES symbol

With ECHOES symbol

For social media platforms, the PlaceMUS XR logo **may be used independently, without the ECHOES symbol**, to simplify the visual presentation; however, all posts must include a textual reference to the Cultural Heritage Cloud in the accompanying description.

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Palette & Typography

The palette reflects the core dimensions of the project, translating music, place and cultural heritage into a coherent visual system.

- **Purple:** associated with music, creativity and technology, represents the expressive and experimental dimension, as well as to digital and xr tools.
- **Green:** referred to landscapes, places and nature, grounding the project in physical locations and cultural environments where musical heritage is situated.
- **Lime accent:** vibrant, energetic and luminous, it highlights interaction, resonance and the links between sound, place and experience.
- **Neutral tones:** provide balance and flexibility across the visual system. They also evoke the material and immaterial layers of cultural heritage, supporting content related to memory, archives and interpretation.

HEX: **#1E1130**

RGB: 30 / 17 / 48

CMYK: 38 / 65 / 0 / 81

HEX: **#002400**

RGB: 0 / 36 / 0

CMYK: 100 / 0 / 100 / 86

HEX: **#191919**

RGB: 25 / 25 / 25

CMYK: 0 / 0 / 0 / 90

HEX: **#6B3DAB**

RGB: 107 / 61 / 171

CMYK: 37 / 64 / 0 / 33

HEX: **#4C751F**

RGB: 76 / 117 / 31

CMYK: 35 / 0 / 74 / 54

HEX: **#F1E9D4**

RGB: 241 / 233 / 212

CMYK: 0 / 3 / 12 / 5

HEX: **#D3B9F8**

RGB: 211 / 185 / 248

CMYK: 15 / 25 / 0 / 3

HEX: **#AFDD7D**

RGB: 175 / 221 / 125

CMYK: 21 / 0 / 43 / 13

HEX: **#E2E83C**

RGB: 226 / 232 / 60

CMYK: 3 / 0 / 74 / 9

WORK SANS

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
j	k	l	m	n	o	p	q	r
s	t	u	v	w	x	y	z	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	.	,	;	:	\$	#	'	!
"	/	?	%	&	()	@	

Work Sans was selected as the **primary typeface** for PlaceMUS XR to ensure **clarity, accessibility and consistency across all digital and communication materials**, supporting a wide and diverse audience.

- Highly legible and inclusive, suitable for users with visual impairments or reading difficulties
- Designed and optimised specifically for digital environments
- Nine available weights, enabling clear hierarchy and structured layouts
- Distinct letterforms that improve character recognition (e.g. lowercase “l” vs uppercase “l”, double-storey “a”)
- Broad language support and reliable rendering across different devices and screen sizes
- Open-source Google Font, freely available and easy to implement across platforms

UNBOUNDED

A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R
S	T	U	V	W	X	Y	Z	
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
j	k	l	m	n	o	p	q	r
s	t	u	v	w	x	y	z	
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
9	.	,	;	:	\$	#	'	!
"	/	?	%	&	()	@	

Unbounded was selected **for the PlaceMUS XR logo** and included in the typographic system for its **strong visual character and expressive qualities.**

Due to its decorative design, Unbounded **presents limitations in terms of accessibility and readability.** For this reason, its use should be limited and complementary, avoiding extended texts or frequent application, and always prioritising Work Sans for clarity and inclusivity.

- Open-source Google Font, freely available and easy to adopt
- Suitable for large-scale communication and display use (e.g. titles, headlines, big visual statements)

Thank you!

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